

Studies on some Less Familiar Ferrocyanogen Complexes. Part VII. Composition of Cobalt (III) Ferro- and Ferricyanides by Electrometric Methods

M. Ajmal and Wahid U. Malik

Direct and reverse titrations between cobaltic sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide, and cobaltic sulphate and potassium ferricyanide have been carried out by conductometric, potentiometric, and amperometric methods. The cobaltic sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide reaction in view of high reduction potential of Co(III)—Co(II) system is expected to provide a complex of the type $\text{Co}_2^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}\text{Cy}_6$. Evidence for this complex has been obtained on the basis of these titrations. Besides a complex having the composition $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6$ is also found to exist. From the cobalt (III)-potassium ferricyanide reaction, adsorption complexes of the type $2\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}\text{Cy}_6$, K_3FeCy_6 and $2\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6$, $3\text{K}_3\text{FeCy}_6$ are obtained besides the normal complex $\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6$. The nature of the reverse amperometric titration curves also supports the formation of adsorption complexes in cobaltic ferricyanide.

Amongst the metal ferrocyanogen complexes, cobalt (III) compounds have attracted little attention by the workers in this field. The only reference worth mentioning is on the spectrophotometric estimation of Fe(II), ferrocyanide, and cerium (III) by cobalt (III) sulphate solution (Bricker and Loeffler, *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, 27, 1419).

On adding cobalt (III) sulphate solution to potassium ferrocyanide, a dark grey precipitate is obtained, which changes to a brown one with excess of cobalt (III). Potassium ferricyanide also reacts with cobalt (III) to give a precipitate with the only difference that the initial colour of the precipitate (brown) does not change on further addition of cobalt (III). Since no work was done till recently on the composition of these freshly precipitated complexes, it was thought worthwhile to take up these studies specially in view of the fact that the interaction between cobalt (III) and potassium ferrocyanide would not be a simple one on account of the high reduction potential of cobalt (III)—cobalt (II) couple (1.82V vs. standard hydrogen electrode).

EXPERIMENTAL

The cobaltic sulphate solution was prepared by the modified method of Bricker and Loeffler (*loc. cit.*). The solution (with crystals in the bottom) obtained was stored in a 250 c.c. glass stoppered flask and kept in a refrigerator at about 0°. The stock solution was diluted with cold 18N- H_2SO_4 prior to use. The strength of the solution was first determined iodometrically. Here the end point was not sharp and therefore the method recommended by Rausch and Kleinberg (T. Moeller, "Inorganic Synthesis", Vol. V, p. 183) was employed. One c.c. of the cobaltic solution was added to 10 c.c. of 0.1N oxalic acid solution. This solution was diluted to 100 c.c. and the unoxidised acid was then titrated by potassium permanganate solution, which was standardised against oxalic acid. The strength was found to be 0.059M and was checked occasionally. The strength did not change even on keeping the solution (in refrigerator) for longer periods.

Potassium ferrocyanide (A.R.) and potassium ferricyanide (recrystallised) were dissolved in double distilled water. The strengths of the solutions were determined volumetrically by titrating against potassium permanganate and sodium thiosulphate respectively (Sutton, "Volumetric Analysis", 10th ed., pp. 270, 220).

The conductivity measurements were carried out by a Cambridge conductivity bridge No. L. 350140 with cell of $k=0.36$, whereas the potentiometric studies were carried out with a Tinsley vernier potentiometer employing bright platinum as the indicator electrode. For the amperometric titrations, the same procedure was employed as given in Parts V and VI (this issue, pp. 297,303) Before carrying out the titrations, a polarogram was taken by introducing 5 c.c. of cobalt(III) sulphate solution in 18*N*-H₂SO₄ with 0.05% gelatin in the polarographic cell. A layer of CCl₄ was put below the solution in order to minimise the possible oxidation of mercury by Co³⁺. Purified nitrogen gas was passed for deaeration and creating an inert atmosphere. The current remained constant in the initial stages, showing a little increase, giving an ill-defined wave, followed by a well-defined reversible wave due to the reduction of cobalt (II) to the metallic state. The titrations were carried out at 0.0 volt and also at 0.8 volt (from the plateau of the first wave). No difference, however, was found by carrying out the titrations at either of these potentials.

The conductance, E.M.F., and current measurements were carried out at 0°. While carrying out the direct titrations [cobalt (III) solution in the burette] the cobaltic sulphate solution was taken in a flask placed in a freezing mixture and pumping the solution into the microburette from it.

FIG. 1. Conductometric titration curves.

- A. 30 c.c. of 0.005 *M*-K₄FeCys against 0.05*N* Co (III) sulphate.
 B. 30 c.c. of 0.02 *M*-K₃FeCys against 0.044 *M* Co (III) sulphate.

Typical curves for the three techniques employed are shown in Figs. 1, 2, and 3 and the results are summarised below. Reverse conductometric titrations could not be performed since the conductance of the cobaltic solution was so high that the addition of potassium ferro- or ferricyanide did not cause an appreciable change in the conductance.

TABLE I

Titrations carried out between Co(III) and K₄FeCy₆.

Conc. of K ₄ FeCy ₆ .	Conc. of Co (III).		Ratio at the inflexion point. Co ³⁺ : FeCy ₆ ⁴⁻ .
	(I) Conductometric.		
0.0100M	0.059M		1:1
0.0066	0.059		1:1
0.0050	0.059		1:1
Direct.	(II) Potentiometric.		
0.02	0.059		1:1
0.01	0.059		1:1
0.005	0.059		1:1
Reverse.			
0.2	0.044		1:1, 1:3
0.2	0.026		1:1, 1:3
0.2	0.020		1:1, 1:3
Direct.	(III) Amperometric.		
0.010	0.0285		1:1
0.005	0.0285		1:1
0.007	0.0285		1:1
Reverse.			
0.2	0.007		1:1
0.2	0.011		1:1
0.2	0.014		1:1

TABLE II

Titrations carried out between Co(III) and K₃FeCy₆.

Conc. of K ₃ FeCy ₆ .	Conc. of Co (III).		Ratio at the inflexion point. Co ³⁺ : FeCy ₆ ³⁻ .
	Conductometric.		
0.020M	0.044M		1:3
0.010	0.044		1:3
0.0066	0.044		1:3
Direct.	Potentiometric.		
0.0180	0.037		1:3
0.0110	0.059		1:3
0.0092	0.059		1:3
Reverse.			
0.2	0.026		1:2, 1:5
0.2	0.025		1:2, 1:5
0.2	0.020		1:2, 1:5
0.2	0.010		1:2, 1:5
Direct.	Amperometric.		
0.020	0.034		1:3
0.015	0.034		1:3
0.010	0.034		1:3
Reverse.			
0.2	0.0080		1:2, 1:5
0.2	0.0069		1:2, 1:5
0.2	0.0051		1:2, 1:5

DISCUSSION

The combining ratio $\text{Co}^{3+} : \text{FeCy}_6^{4-}$ as 1:1, obtained from the direct potentiometric and conductometric titrations and also from direct and reverse amperometric titrations, would normally point towards the formation of the complex $\text{KCo}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}\text{Cy}_6$. Such a reaction, however, is not possible in view of the high reduction potential of Co (III)—Co(II) system. For the reaction:

the value of K , calculated from the values -0.356 (for $\text{FeCy}_6^{4-} = \text{FeCy}_6^{3-} + e$) and -1.82 (for $\text{Co}^{3+} + e = \text{Co}^{2+}$), is 6.3×10^{25} . The high value of K indicates that the potassium ferrocyanide would be oxidised to the ferricyanide, whereas the cobalt (III) is reduced to cobalt (II). Under these conditions the reaction between cobaltic sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide can take either of the following courses:

followed by

- (i) $2\text{CoSO}_4 + \text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6 \longrightarrow \text{Co}_2^{\text{II}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}\text{Cy}_6 + 2\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$, or
- (ii) $\text{CoSO}_4 + \text{K}_3\text{FeCy}_6 \longrightarrow \text{KCo}^{\text{II}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6 + \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$, or
- (iii) $\text{Co}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 + 2\text{K}_3\text{FeCy}_6 \longrightarrow 2\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6 + 3\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$

FIG. 2. Potentiometric titration curves.

Direct. A. 10 c.c. of 0.02 M - K_4FeCy_6 against 0.059 M -Co (III) sulphate.

Reverse. B. 10 c.c. of 0.025 M -Co (III) sulphate against 0.2 M - K_4FeCy_6 .

Reverse. C. 10 c.c. of 0.01 M -Co (III) sulphate against 0.2 M - K_3FeCy_6 .

Direct. D. 10 c.c. of 0.018 M - K_3FeCy_6 against 0.037 M -MCo (III) sulphate.

The formation of the above three complexes would depend not only on the presence of excess of either of the reactants in the reaction mixture but also on their affinity for each other. For example, Bricker and Loeffler (*loc. cit.*) reported the existence of the complex $\text{Co}_3(\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6)_2$ by the interaction of cobalt (III) and potassium ferrocyanide even when

potassium ferrocyanide was in excess. As regards the stoichiometric equations representing the overall reaction for the possible complexes for the cobalt (III)—potassium ferrocyanide reaction, we have:

Since the ratio 1:1 for the reactants is obtained at the inflection points from the direct potentiometric and conductometric titrations as well as from the direct and reverse amperometric titrations, the complex formed would be CoIIIFeIIICy_6 according to the equation (c). Proof for the formation of cobaltous ferrocyanide, predominance of which should always be expected on the redox nature of the reaction, is also forthcoming on the basis of the reverse potentiometric titrations. It may thus be concluded that besides the formation of cobaltous ferrocyanide, cobaltic ferricyanide complex is also likely to be formed during the interaction of cobaltic sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide.

On adding cobalt(III) sulphate solution to potassium ferricyanide, the combining ratio $\text{Co}^{3+} : \text{FeCy}_6^{3-}$ comes out to be 1:3 (direct conductometric, potentiometric, and amperometric titrations, Figs. 1, 2, and 3) whereas for the reverse order of mixing, the ratios are 1:2 and 1:5 (reverse potentiometric and amperometric titrations; Figs. 2 and 3).

FIG. 3. Amperometric titration curves.

- Direct. A. 20 c.c. of 0.01 *M*- K_4FeCy_6 against 0.029 *M*-Co (III) sulphate.
 B. 20 c.c. of 0.02 *M*- K_3FeCy_6 against 0.034 *M*-Co (III) sulphate.
 Reverse. C. 20 c.c. of 0.007 *M*-Co (III) sulphate against 0.2 *M*- K_4FeCy_6 .
 D. 20 c.c. of 0.008 *M*-Co (III) sulphate against 0.2 *M*- K_3FeCy_6 .

The ratio 1:2 would point towards the formation of the complex CoIIIFeIIICy_6 according to the equation:

The ratios 1:3 and 1:5 would obviously form adsorption complexes having the composition $2\text{CoFeCy}_6 \cdot \text{K}_3\text{FeCy}_6$ and $2\text{CoFeCy}_6 \cdot 3\text{K}_3\text{FeCy}_6$ respectively.

The existence of the adsorption complexes can also be inferred from the reverse amperometric titration curves (Fig. 3). On adding potassium ferricyanide to cobaltic sulphate solution, the current goes on decreasing after which it remains constant for a wide

range of the added titrant and then increases. The horizontal part of the curve might represent conditions where the freshly precipitated cobaltic ferricyanide complex strongly adsorbs the ferricyanide ions.

Thanks of authors are due to Dr. A. R. Kidwai, Head of the Department of Chemistry, for providing facilities and to C. S. I.R. (India) for awarding a fellowship to one of them (M.A.) to carry out this work.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
MUSLIM UNIVERSITY,
ALIGARH.

Received January 11, 1961.